

ROLE OF LEADERS RE-DESIGNING SPORTS (INDUSTRY) MANAGEMENT

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Abstract:

Sporting functional areas in industry require a multidimensional perspective. Developments and technological breakthroughs in today's world's sports organizations have made it imperative to take asymmetric variables into account, along with symmetrical ones. Because the form opponent and struggle will take will mean the absolute defeat of one-dimensional system of thinking. The goal of this research is to identify the role and functions of leaders in the frame of the level of the reach of the sports industry in the world. This research has been examined in accordance with qualitative research methods, phenomenological design and the descriptive approach. Sports management within the sport industry will need leaders who can make the right decisions through an effective judgment process, which requires multidimensional thinking, uncertainty and rapid reaction in unexpected situations. The leadership qualities and reasoning techniques and methods that have to be possessed in order to find solutions to institutional problems have increased in terms of significance by using the reasoning ability of the leading personnel who take roles in all the functional areas and all levels of sports organizations.

Keywords: leadership, thinking, reasoning, decision, success, creativity

1. Introduction

With the end of the Cold War, there have been many changes in the political, social, economic and military arenas; paradigms and strategies were deeply shaken; the rule of

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linear logic was replaced with an environment which is full of ambiguities.

Sporting functional areas in industry require a multidimensional perspective. Developments and technological breakthroughs in today's world's sports organizations have made it imperative to take asymmetric variables into account, along with symmetrical ones. Because the form opponent and struggle will take will mean the absolute defeat of one-dimensional system of thinking. Sporting organizations in the sport industry will need leaders who can make the right decisions through an effective process of reasoning, which requires multidimensional thinking, uncertainty and rapid reaction in unexpected situations.

The most important function for the leaders of sports organizations will be "decision making". It is expected that the leaders who will serve on the basis of the specified conditions will have an intensive judgment process in order to reach the most efficient output as a result of the "decision making" function. Evaluation of "competition" and "struggle", which are the most important concepts on professional sportsmen in particular, has come under the pressure of an unknown and unpredictable future. Leaders, who will actively work in the sports industry, need to incorporate multi-faceted qualities in order to adapt to the changing character of the sporting field, especially the fast pace.

2. Methodology of the Research

The goal of this research is to identify the role and functions of leaders in the frame of the level of the reach of the sports industry in the world. This research was examined in accordance with qualitative research method. It was also primarily utilized the descriptive analysis method in order to understand what the collected data said or what results revealed relating to research problem. In this research, the data were collected by interview technique. As interview technique, "Patton's interview guide approach" was used. Prepared in the form of open-ended and semi-structured questions, the questions in interview form are semi-structured and prearranged.

This research was conducted through face to face interviews with two managers who are the members of Board or work as a General Manager/Administrative Manager in their clubs that operate in TFF Sport Toto Super League in Turkey.

I have chosen Phenomenological studies to examine human experiences through the descriptions provided by the people involved. These experiences are called lived experiences. The goal of phenomenological studies is to describe the meaning that experiences hold for each subject. This type of research is used to study areas in which there is little knowledge.

3. Literature Review

3.1. Impacts of Information Age on Organizations

The most important factor faced by today's organizations, where technological and social developments change rapidly through globalization, is the uncertainty of international competition, rapid change through communication technologies, aging of knowledge, an unstable world and future. This has led organizations as living organisms, to live in a more dynamic environment and in an unpredictable but designable future.

Rise of globalization and global thinking system, information becoming the most important source, corporate governance and strategic alliances stand out among the factors that push organizations to make fundamental changes. (İşcan, Ömer Faruk and Naktiyok, Atılhan, 2005)

A. Globalization

It is important for the organizational managers have a system of global thinking within the challenging and compulsory competitive conditions in a period where all the markets, including sports, are globalized.

Parallel to the global system of thinking, organizations must consider the global arena as a chessboard, by acting with the understanding of global customer, global purchasing, global knowledge, global industry and global competition to win, even though the squares are not equal. (Naktiyok & Atılhan, 2004)

B. Intellectual Knowledge

Organizations will be able to come to the forefront in the competition by transforming their knowledge and experience to create new values. The quality of the information, which is among the most valuable assets of organizations, stands out as the most important force multiplier instead of quantity. Knowledge, which is considered as a strategic resource, has become a management function which aims to reach at a new form in product and service within a new area of application and with creative ideas. C.

C. Governance

Corporate governance in information age covers the relation of senior management which is responsible for the strategic management and direction of organization with the shareholders, employees, suppliers, customers and other social rules that consider themselves as beneficiaries on the organization and it means the management of senior managers of organization. (Ülgen, 2004)

3.2 Main Skills of the Information Age Organizations

In the age of information, the essence of organizations consists of necessary information to be accessed in a timely manner and on the most economical way and to be shared with the organization to create added value. The organization must have some abilities

to win this feature. These are flexibility, innovation, knowledge management, horizontal organizational structure and continuous learning.

A. Flexibility

Organizations need to have flexible management and service / production processes in order to adapt with globalization and the rapidly changing dynamics of information. Flexibility, which is the capacity to adapt to circumstances under unpredictable circumstances, is the most basic feature of information age organizations.

B. Horizontal Organizational Structure

As an organization becomes more knowledge intensive, the number of managers and administrators will decrease, knowledge will be under the control experts who basically do different jobs and tend to manage themselves. Thus, the organizational structure will shift from centralism and autonomous units will become more important. (Bejerse, 1999) In this respect, information-oriented organizations are transforming their fields of activity in a rapidly changing environment into an organizational structure that can be easily adapted to change and with flat lines within the structure.

C. Innovative (Continuous Improvement and Change)

Innovation is the most basic feature of information-based organizations because any product or service placed into the market is rapidly duplicated. Because of this, organizations have to rapidly transform their knowledge in a competitive environment to meet any new requirements as product life spans are rapidly decreasing.

D. Knowledge Management

Knowledge Management is the ability to rapidly obtain information that contributes the competitive power, to transfer it quickly into the organizational structure and to use it effectively in organizational processes. The basis of the knowledge management system is to replace the outdated information with the new one and use it in a way to form services.

The key to provide this advantage is the structuralization of knowledge creation process. (Özveren, Mina and Gursu, Mehmet, 2004) The transformation of structuralization into an organizational culture is one of the most fundamental issues of information age organizations in knowledge management.

E. Organizational Learning

The most important fact that defines the information society is the abundance of knowledge and generation of new knowledge. Immediately replacing the continuously outdated information with new one is the most significant feature of being updated. When we consider the subject from this perspective, the continuity of learning will become a key component in business life.

When organizations realize that the concept of learning means competitive advantage, they define their primary purpose as continuous learning and learning organizations. (Tepeci, Mustafa and Koçak, 2005)

3.3 Human Resources in Information Age Organizations

The organizations can sustain their activities in today's work ecology, increase their profits and adapt to the highly competitive environments through highly qualified individuals. (Demirci, 2002) Especially in information-based organizations, human resources play a role that strongly complements physical capital. (DeLong, and Lawrence, 2001)

The ability to convert the production factors from the indispensable parameter of competitive environment, new human type will only be possible in the learning organization structure, via organizational commitment and acting as a team and the ability to use initiative. Effective management, in other words, the ability to direct the group of people with such abilities to reach the corporate goals of an organization can only be achieved with effective leadership.

3.4 Effective Leadership in the New Age

In recent age, when knowledge is readily available to all, leaders need to have a much more internalized level of knowledge than the society they are managing so that they can effectively carry out their tasks.

The success of the leaders is measured with whether they can help their organization to reach the desired goal or not. Leaders who can bring out the talents of all the individuals involved in the organization through scientific methods and in the most appropriate way and aggregate them in common product with the participation of everyone will be successful leaders of today and the future. New leadership skills (James, 1997) that need to differ from past leaders in order to be effective in the dynamic environmental conditions of new age: To have a new perspective, To Identify the Future, To Use The Power of Myths and Symbols, To Understand the Past in order to Know the Future, To Do More or To Do More with Less, Mastering in New Forms of Mind, To Benefit from Diversity.

3.5 Sports Industry in the New Age

The world, which has turned into an economically large market with the impact of globalization, has expanded to include sports with the development of information and communication technologies and created a new market environment in terms of production and service as well as in organizational terms.

Today, Sport managements and practices have been undergoing a rapid change over the past 20 years. In this process, the organizational structure of the clubs, the size of their revenues, the characteristics of fans, the physical conditions and qualifications of the stadium, the physical and technical capacities of the athletes, the tactical and technical application skills of the managers and the printed and visual media of sports have changed rapidly.

3.6 Club Management Functional Areas

Within the Sports Industry, it is very important for sports managers to plan the organizational goals for the administration board, football players and technical personnel's administration, to put these plans into action and control those by referring to the relation between science and sport and while doing all these, the organizational structure should be considered. On the other hand, regarding the issues such as marketing, product development and event organization, the environment (fans-group) to be considered (Breuer, 2011).

Aforementioned activity areas of the clubs are tried to be managed by separating into functional areas in 8 different categories.

- Commercial business development,
- Advertisement and Marketing
- Economy and Finance
- Corporate Communication (Press, Public Relations)
- Athlete Training
- Infrastructure,
- Professional Team,
- Relations with Fans,
- Sports Facilities Management,

Evaluation of two important concepts with considerable thought by professional sportsmen; "Competitor" and "struggle" have become under the pressure of an unknown and undetermined future within the multi-dimensional sportive function areas.

3.7 Nature of Reasoning

Reasoning consists as a mental ability of the individual and emerges in the advanced stages of human thought. (Umay, 2003) Reasoning can also be expressed as argumentation, is the process of thinking through all the factors and reaching to a rational conclusion.

Reasoning is human-specific and it is a skill that emerges in the advanced stages of thinking. Reasoning is an activity that involves a variety of ways of thinking. Reasoning cannot be done without critical and creative thinking.

Although at an advanced level, if a thought is not based on knowledge, if it cannot be justified and if it does not contain any logical approaches, then it cannot be considered as reasoning. The nature of reasoning is evaluated together with Intelligence, Reasoning, Stages in Thought and Reasoning and the Methods of Reasoning that can be used.

Intelligence is the ability of a person to present a product that is valued in one or more cultures or to solve a problem that he or she has encountered in daily life or in professional life in an effective and productive way. (Güngör 2007) Ability to perceive the relation between abstract or concrete objects with the help of concepts and perceptions, abstract thinking, reasoning and the ability to use these mental functions in a concerted way.

Thinking appears in a very wide range such as "remembering", "simple thinking", "critical thinking" and "creative thinking", which is from simple to complex. (Krulik and Rudnick, 1993)

3.7.1 Stages of Reasoning

The individual's reasoning process is discussed in five stages (D'Zurilla and Goldfried, 1971). These are the general approach, defining of problem, the creation of options, decision making and evaluation.

General approach begins with deciding to solve the problem. It is a mental tendency that can be either supportive or obstructive in nature, which allows the individual to adopt or reject a particular solution, and which leads the individual to behave in a certain way.

In the process of *defining the problem*, the person collects the information necessary to identify the problem after eliminating all the obstacles to solving the problem. This stage is about the definition and format of the problem.

In the course of *creation of options*; the person uses his creativity and crosses the individual and social boundaries and freely generates ideas. The generated ideas enable the creation of possible options to solve the problem.

The creation of options naturally requires selection because it is a goal-oriented process. Research findings indicate that the choice of information is not a function of the individual's past experiences, but on the contrary, the ability to use past experiences is an important factor.

In the *decision-making stage*; individual selects one of these options by using the decision-making method.

This process can be defined as selecting a specific one among a number of options for action. The purpose of the decision-making process is to help a person to enter a number of actions that will increase his/her chances of being satisfied with his/her own decisions. It has been determined that making a successful decision depends on some skills. These are:

- Information,
- Accurately evaluating the possibilities,
- Evaluating the beneficial parts of decisions,
- Evaluating the results of a multiple choices.

During the evaluation phase, the individual evaluates the proposal of the solution taking into consideration the possible problems that could emerge as well as the knowledge about the subject in order to be able to make a right decision.

3.7.2 Reasoning Techniques

In order to be able to do this correctly, the General Reasoning Techniques, which have proven their success in the world, are used at every stage of this process. These are: Multiple Intelligence Techniques, Critical Thinking Techniques, Brain Based Learning Techniques, Stress Control Techniques, Understanding Complex Situations Techniques, Creative Thinking Techniques, Effective Decision Making Techniques and Project Planning and Managing Skills. Having these skills will be the most important features for a strong leadership profile.

4. Discussion

Information age organization; is very flexible and it gives a positive response to ambiguities, complexity and change, constantly creates new information, turns this knowledge into the knowledge of organization, uses it in organizational processes through information sharing, adapts to the environment, and makes its decisions easily, (Atak, 2003)

Clubs, as one of the Information Age sports organizations, have to consider the people, systems, processes and structure that establish the organization with an integrative approach in the functional areas in order to increase the competition and improve the quality. Process management, implementation of plans and programs to reform people and improve their skills and confidence should be the basis for all works carried out.

Sportive function areas; will guide the leading personnel into deliberate, uncertain and complex situations in terms of perspective of reasoning, initiative and leadership. The most important function for the leaders of sports organizations will be

"decision making". An intensive process of reasoning is expected from the leaders who will serve on the specified conditions to reach the most efficient output as a result of the "decision making" function.

Leaders who can vitalize the competitors in a good way, who can make the right decisions through an effective reasoning process, who can evaluate the effects of factors other than themselves on their own group, will be successful in sports fields in the future which will be shaped by technological developments.

No matter how institutionalized an organization is, the burden of ultimate decision at critical moments is often in the hands of a few people. In the present conditions, those who can understand the true importance of the data, measure their accuracy and use their intuition well can make the right decisions. Therefore, effective leadership is the most important multiplier force in an organization and it requires an artistic point of view.

Leaders with advanced reasoning ability have sufficient knowledge in their field of activity and can examine and discover new situations with all the dimensions, make logical assumptions, justify their thoughts, reach some conclusions, and explain and defend the conclusion reached.

In other words, the Reasoning ability of the Leaders is a human-specific capability which emerges in the advanced stages of thinking. It is scientifically recognized that it can be learned even if it has personal differences.

5. Conclusion

Sports organizations in the sport industry need to have multifaceted skills and new leadership skills in order to be able to adapt actively to the changing character of the sports field, especially the fast pace, in accordance with the information dynamics of the sport, especially within the sports clubs.

Within the sports industry, sport management will need leaders who can make the right decisions through an effective process of reasoning, which requires multidimensional thinking and rapid reaction in uncertain and unexpected situations.

Leaders who manage sporting core functional areas are expected to achieve the most efficient outcome as a result of decision-making functions, using thought-judgment-initiative-creativity features and leadership skills very well when confronting sensitive, uncertain and complex situations within a broad task spectrum.

For the success of the organization, continuously producing value and having wide alternatives will be among the most important criteria. The increase of alternatives will indicate the strength; the restriction of preference will indicate the weakness. It will be essential to create many different action areas for each situation and event.

This will be accomplished by strong leaders who will be able to keep as many alternatives as possible, that is to say, to keep the initiatives wide at all times and to act with sufficient self-confidence and determination.

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